

A Study on Work Life Balance of College Staffs At Villupuram District

D. Shoba¹, Dr. G. Suganthi²

¹Assistant Professor Dept of Management Studies

²Head & Associate Professor Dept of Management Studies

¹Theivanai Ammal College for Women, Villupuram, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Government Arts College, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract- In the recent decades, there has been a dramatic growth in the amount of researches enhanced to understand the connectivity between work and family and/or personal life. Work Life Balance (WLB) has gained attention in educational sector especially in colleges at Villupuram district. However, there is a need to explore the subject vis-à-vis teaching staffs, keeping in mind the increasing cases of work life problems among teaching staffs in colleges. Thus, the purpose of this study is to map the dimensions of WLB among teaching staffs. This study is based on the responses of teaching staffs both men and woman from colleges in Villupuram district. Research instrument designed on the basis of literature survey and then data was collected. In all 150 responses were generated. In this scale refinement was done using percentage analysis. The percentage of analysis from the table was found majority of teaching staffs on the any WLB dimensions. Inter item Convergent validity was high. This study may give insight regarding the problem that teaching staffs usually face. Balance should be established between workload distribution, time and extra-curricular activities so as to inculcate efficiency among teaching staffs. The study is based on a limited sample size. There is a need to carry out studies with a larger sample size to make results more generalized. Work-life Balance, educational qualification, time spend at work and work life balance policy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The term 'Work-life Balance' was first coined in 1986 in reaction to the unhealthy choices in the work place, as they opted to neglect family, friends and leisure activities in the pursuit of corporate / work goals. Striking a balance between work and family life is one of the major problems faced by every employee. Men are who take time off or reduce working hours for taking care of the family experience similar discrimination. Most of employees both male and female lives are becoming more consumed with a host of family and other personal responsibility and interests today. Therefore, in an effort to retain employees, it is increasingly important for organizations to recognize this balance.

Today's married worker is typically part of dual-career couples, which makes it difficult to find time to meet commitments to family, friends and community. But if you're spending most of your time at work, your home life will likely pay the price. Consider the pros cons of working extra hours on your work-life balance. They may miss out on important events, such as your child's first bike ride, your father's 60th birthday or your high school reunion. Missing out on important milestone may harm relationship with your loved ones. Trusted friends are a key part of your support system. But if you're spending time at the office instead of with them, you'll find it difficult to nurture those friendships. If you're regularly worked extra hours, you may be given more responsibility. This could create a never-ending and increasing cycle, causing more concerns and challenges.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shreyas B (2017) has concluded that to achieve work life balance has become an important subject since the time has changed from earning the family living in today's world, where both men and woman equally share the responsibility of earning for the betterment of their family life. The quality of health, problems in time management and lack of proper social support are the major factor influencing the work life balance of professionals in India.

Mari S and Haja Mohideen O. M (2015) they are studied the work life balance has been one of the major factors in influencing the organization's efficiency. The present study has been carried out to evaluate the nature of Work Life Balance, as experienced by professionals in Indian context. For this purpose a survey was carried out to estimate a Work Life Balance Index of professionals and also highlights the issues connected with work life balance of faculty in educational institutions and the factors that determine work life balance.

Sudha and karthikeyan P (2014) has concluded that to achieve work life balance, every woman should set the goal and excel both in career and family. Some of the strategies and

skills at work such as planning, organizing and setting limits can be used at home and work place for accomplishing a satisfying and fulfilling well balanced life both professionally and personally. The study is focused on impact of work life conflict on job performance of female school teachers. Result showed that work life conflict has a negative impact on job performance of female employees and organization policies do not moderate this relationship.

Statement of problem

The present study is to describe the balancing life between responsibilities a work and responsibilities outside work among Teaching Staff's.

Objectives of the study:

- To know attitude of the staff towards their work
- To analyze work life balance policies enhanced by the institution to improve the work life balance of college teachers

Research methodology

Convenient sampling method used in this study. The samples are teaching staff's and the sample size is 150 Teachers from 154 colleges in Villupuram district. Primary data was collected from 150 teachers through questionnaire and secondary data were collected from various online resources.

Data analysis and interpretation

Table 1: The Age of the respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 33	58	38.7
34 to 43	65	43.3
44 to 53	12	8.0
Above 54 Years	15	10.0
Total	150	100

Source: Primary data computed

The above table shows that 43.3% of the respondents belong to 34 -43 age, 38.7% of the respondents belong to below 33 years and 8.0% of the respondents belong to 44 – 53 years.10 % of the respondents are above 54 years.

Table 2: Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
PG (Only)	56	37.33
M.Phil	57	38.00
PhD	37	24.67
Total	150	100.0

Source: Primary data computed

The above table shows that 38.00% of the respondents belong to M. Phil qualification, 37.33% of the respondents belong to PG (Only) and finally 24.67% of the respondents belong to Ph. D the majority of teaching staff qualification is M. Phil.

Table 3: Amount of time spend at work

Attitude / Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Very unhappy	20	14
Unhappy	30	20
Indifferent	15	10
Very happy	85	56
Total	150	100

Source: Primary data computed

The above table shows that 56 % of the respondents are says that very happy to spend time for work, 20% of the respondents are says that Unhappy, 14% of the respondents are says that very unhappy and 10 % of the respondents are indifferent. The majority of statement is very happy to time spending on work because of students are very excellent in colleges.

Table 4: Work life balance policy

Work life balance	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	27	18
Agree	37	24
Indifferent	54	36
Disagree	24	16
Strongly agree	8	6
Total	150	100

Source: Primary data computed

The above table shows that 36 % of the respondents are says that Indifferent as work life policy, 24 % of the respondents are Agree, 18 % of the respondents are Strongly agree with the work life balance, 16 % of the respondents are says that Disagree, and 6 % of the respondents are strongly agree.

III. FINDINGS

The above table shows that 43.3% of the respondents belong to 34 -43 age, 38.7% of the respondents belong to below 33 years and 8.0% of the respondents belong to 44 – 53 years.10 % of the respondents are above 54 years.

The above table shows that 38.00% of the respondents belong to M. Phil qualification, 37.33% of the respondents belong to PG (Only) and finally 24.67% of the respondents belong to PhD the majority of teaching staff qualification is M. Phil.

The above table shows that 56 % of the respondents are says that very happy to spend time for work, 20% of the respondents are says that Unhappy, 14% of the respondents are says that very unhappy and 10 % of the respondents are indifferent. The majority of statement is very happy to time spending on work because of students are very excellent in colleges.

The above table shows that 36 % of the respondents are says that Indifferent as work life policy, 24 % of the respondents are Agree, 18 % of the respondents are Strongly agree with the work life balance, 16 % of the respondents are says that Disagree, and 6 % of the respondents are strongly agree.

IV. SUGGESTIONS

The colleges can provide facilities like laptops to work from home, child care center to bring their children to work place occasionally; this will help them to balance their work life equally without tired or depression. The college can make arrangements for conducting health programs, counseling services, parenting and family support programs to reduce the employees stress, inferiority complex, fear of failures, emotion and angry. Female teaching staffs have to be support by their family members, which will help them to reduce the personal life stresses.

V. CONCLUSION

Work-life balance is about creating and maintaining supportive and healthy work environments, which will enable

employees to have balance between work and personal responsibilities and thus strengthen employee loyalty and productivity. The present study is aim at identifying the work-life balance and perception of the women academician views on their working institution. From this study it is apparent that the teaching staffs are aware about their work-life balance which is evident from the response of the respondents. The majority of the respondents have the positive attitude towards the prevailing work-life balance. The most respondents perceive that the work-life balance is favorable for them. The overall assessment of the work-life balance state that the most of respondents have a positive perception of the various dimensions of their institution. The most the employees perceived the work-life balance has positive influence on the Institutional development.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shreyas B (2017). Work Life Balance of Married Female Teaching Staff of Selected School's of Dakshina Kannada District, International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management Vol. 6, No.1, pp 8-10.
- [2] Mari S and Haja Mohideen O. M (2015). A study of work-life balance among the college teachers in Pudukkottai and Thanjavur districts, International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology, Vol. 2 Issue 7, pp 127-132.
- [3] Meharaj A (2015). Work- Life Balance of Faculty Members in Autonomous Colleges International Journal of Recent Research Aspects Vol. 2, Issue 3 pp. 48-49
- [4] Sudha J & P Karthikeyan,(2014). Work Life Balance of Women Employee: A Literature Review, International Journal of Management Research and Review, Vol.4, Issue 8 pp. 797-804.
- [5] Saranya S and Gokulakrishnan A (2013). Work Life Balance among Women Academician with Reference to Colleges in Chennai Asian Journal of Managerial Science Vol. 2 No. 2, pp. 21-29.
- [6] Encyclopedia Villupuram district.